

STUDENT PERFORMANCE AND LEARNING OUTCOMES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Dr. P. S. Aithal* & P. M. Suresh Kumar**

* Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, Karnataka

** Srinivas Institute of Management studies, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, Karnataka

Abstract:

In higher education, learning outcomes are the specifications of what a student should learn and demonstrate, on successful completion of the course or the programme. It can also be seen as the desired outcome of the learning process in terms of acquisition of the skills and knowledge. They are embedded in the curriculum. Achieving learning outcomes needs specific experiences to be provided to the students and evaluation of their attainment. A programme without stated learning objectives and outcomes that are not evaluated or assessed gets neglected in implementation. Hence all the stated learning outcomes must be part of the evaluation protocol of the programme. Student assessment provides an indication of the areas where learning has happened and where it has to be improved upon. In this paper, we have analysed the strategies followed by Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Mangalore for student performance. Issues like the clearly stated learning outcomes of the college and the details on how the students and staff are made aware of these, institutional efforts to monitor and communicate the progress and performance of students throughout the duration of the course/programme, and the analysis of the students results/achievements to see the differences if any, patterns of achievement across the programmes/courses offered, structure of the teaching, learning and assessment strategies of the institution to facilitate the achievement of the intended learning outcomes, and the measures/initiatives taken up by the institution to enhance the social and economic relevance of the courses offered are discussed. The institutions effort to collect and analyse data on student learning outcomes and use it for planning and overcoming barriers of learning, institution and individual teachers use assessment/evaluation as an indicator for evaluating student performance, achievement of learning objectives and planning, and other relevant information regarding teaching-learning and evaluation are also discussed.

Index Terms: Student Performance in Higher Education Institution & Learning Outcomes in Higher Education

1. Introduction:

In higher education system, learning outcomes are the specifications of what a student should learn and demonstrate on successful completion of the course or the programme. It can also be seen as the desired outcome of the learning process in terms of acquisition of the skills and knowledge. Achieving learning outcomes need specific experiences to be provided to the students and evaluation of their attainment. Student assessment provides an indication of the areas where learning has happened and where it has to be improved upon. This paper is a discussion of the educational service model developed by Srinivas Institute of Management Studies for integrated academic support. The college has been providing education service in major areas of importance to the society namely Information Technology, Business Management and Social Service with stated learning outcome. Institutional strategies are deployed to attain these [1-6]. The measures /initiatives taken up by the institution to enhance the social and economic relevance of the courses offered, institutions effort to collect and analyse data on student learning outcomes and its use for planning and overcoming barriers is

discussed here.

Several studies on innovations and quality in higher education including : Student's perceptions of quality in higher education [2], Educational institutions quest for service quality: customers perspective [3], Quality Teaching and Learning as Practice Within Different Disciplinary Discourses [4], Strategic Planning in Higher Education Institutions [5], Innovations and Best Practices can Transform Higher Education Institutions [6], Quality in higher education [7-8], Internal Quality Assurance Cell and its Contribution [9], Enhancement of Graduate attributes in Higher Education Institutions through Stage Models [10], Quality Enhancement in Higher Education Institutions [11], Effective Leadership and Governance [12], Strategy Development and Deployment in Higher Education Institutions [13], Faculty Empowerment Strategies in Higher Education Institutions [14], Unique & Successful Model in Integrated Development [15], Applying SWOC Analysis to an Institution of Higher Education [16], Techniques for Electric Energy Auditing in Education System [17], Societal Expectation And Institutional Accountability in Higher Education [18], Methods and Approaches for Employability Skill Generation in Higher Educational Institutions [19], Quality Enhancement in Higher Education Institutions through Best Practices in Library [20], Analysis of Academic Administrative System Implemented in Higher educational institution [21], Learning through Team Centric Exercise & Key Point Pedagogy - An effective Learning Model for Slow Learners in Higher Education Training [22], Opportunities and Challenges for Private Universities [23], Innovations in Private Universities [24], Creating Innovators through setting up organizational Vision, Mission and Core Values : a Strategic Model in Higher Education [25], Comparative Study on MBA Programmes in Private & Public Universities [26], Impact of On-line Education on Higher Education System [27], Innovations in Higher Education - A new model implemented in MCA degree programme [28], Environmental Consciousness in Higher Educational Institutions [29], Analysis of Choice Based Credit System in Higher Education [30], Innovations in Student Centric Learning – A Study of Top Business Schools [31], Innovations in Experimental Learning – A Study of World Top Business Schools [32], How to Increase Research Productivity in Higher Educational Institutions [33], Academic Support through Information System [34], Innovative Education Model to realize Ideal Education System [35], ABCD analysis of Stage Model in Higher Education [36],) Analysis of NAAC Accreditation System using ABCD framework [37], Application of ABCD Analysis Framework on Private University System [38], The Study of New National Institutional Ranking System using ABCD Framework [39], are studied and published. In this paper, we have analysed the strategies followed by Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Mangalore for its student performance issues like the clearly stated learning outcomes of the college and the details on how the students and staff are made aware of these, institutional efforts to monitor and communicate the progress and performance of students through the duration of the course/programme and the analysis of the students results/achievements and the differences if any and patterns of achievement across the programmes/courses offered, structure of the teaching, learning and assessment strategies of the institution to facilitate the achievement of the intended learning outcomes, the measures/initiatives taken up by the institution to enhance the social and economic relevance of the courses offered. The outcomes like the institutions effort to collect and analyse data on student learning outcomes and use it for planning and overcoming barriers of learning, institution and individual teachers use assessment/evaluation as an indicator for evaluating student

performance, achievement of learning objectives and planning, and other relevant information regarding Teaching-Learning and Evaluation are also analysed.

2. Student Performance:

The Learning Outcomes: The College does have clearly stated learning outcomes. Some of the learning outcomes that college aims to achieve are stated in Vision, Mission and Objectives of the college. Some of the stated learning outcomes are as follows:

- ✓ Subject knowledge
- ✓ Intellectual capabilities
- ✓ Character building
- ✓ Emotional maturity
- ✓ Social maturity
- ✓ Business acumen
- ✓ Professionalism
- ✓ Employability skills
- ✓ Scientific temper
- ✓ Strategic thinking
- ✓ Values & Ethics
- ✓ Morality

The learning outcomes are clearly reflected in the vision, mission and objectives of the institute. This is imparted to the students through information (from college calendar to hoardings visibly mounted in the college) and action (through equipping them in all realms of life ranging from employability skills to character building).

The learning outcomes are clearly made aware to the faculty members through the organizational culture which any new member get acquainted in course of time.

Institutional Strategies:

Institutional efforts to monitor and communicate the progress and performance of students throughout the duration of the course/programme and the analysis of the students' results/achievements and the differences if any and patterns of achievement across the programmes/courses offered are the following:

- ✓ **Classroom Monitoring** - There is a continuous evaluation system through classroom assignments, presentations, group activities, case study analysis and laboratory performance. The concerned subject faculty assesses the students individually on the basis of their knowledge of the subject, communication skills, presentation skills and creativity.
- ✓ **Attendance** - The College maintains the attendance record of individual students in all subjects throughout the semester. Periodically (monthly) this is assessed for shortage and such instances are conveyed to the parents of respective students through SMS. The college strictly follows the mandatory attendance requirement of the University.
- ✓ **Internal Assessment test** - The College conducts three internal tests in a semester including preparatory exam. The evaluated answer booklets are given to the students to convince them of their performance. If the performance of any student is falling short of standard level, the respective lecturer will seek explanation for the poor performance.
- ✓ **Declaration Form for Absence in the Class** - The college has an innovative practice of keeping students alert against absenting in the class. This is followed through a declaration form to be submitted to the concerned faculty for each hour of absence. The declaration form contains information about total number of classes conducted, number of classes attended by the concerned students,

reason for absence, signature of the student countersigned by the faculty and maintained in his possession. This helps in tracking the instances of losing the classes.

- ✓ **Declaration Form by Parents & Student for Attendance Shortage:** In every semester, at the time of paying examination fee for the University, the students who have attendance shortage is required to submit a declaration form which is also signed by his/her parents stating that he/she is aware of the rules regarding attendance requirements and will abide by the regulations so that student gets an opportunity to take effort to compensate the shortage during the remaining period of time and becomes eligible to take the exam.
- ✓ **Communication of Attendance and Internal Marks by SMS:** The College conveys the attendance as well as the marks of each student to his parents through the SMS at the close of every month. Software has been developed particularly for this purpose by the college.
- ✓ **Counselling for Parents of Poor Performers:** Apart from intimating the marks of internal exams periodically, the college also invites parents of poor performers and counsel them.
- ✓ **Handing Over The Semester End Marks Cards to the Students Along With their Parents:** The College recognizes the stake of the parents in the performance of their wards. Therefore, the University examination marks cards are handed over to the students in presence of their parents.
- ✓ **Results & Achievements:** The following tables present an analysis of students results/achievements course wise for last four years reflecting the differences and patterns of achievements across the courses /programmes.

Teaching, Learning, and Assessment Strategies:

The teaching, learning and assessment strategies of the institution are structured to realize the intended learning outcomes mentioned above:

Subject Knowledge: The components constituting the teaching, learning and assessment strategy for acquiring subject knowledge are (1) teachers, (2) Books and teaching materials (3) Motivation for teaching and learning and (4) Evaluation of both teaching and learning. The institution strives to create a learning environment which is essentially student centric.

Intellectual Capabilities: Through our teaching- learning model the curricular, co-curricular and extra-curricular activities are geared to boosting creativity, challenge of thinking out-of-the box and encouraging free expression of ideas.

Character Building: The institute exposes its members to spiritual development and character building, through programs conducted in association with organizations such as Sri Ramakrishna Mutt and Vivekananda Study Circle.

Emotional Maturity: This is built-up rather involuntarily. The teachers act as models to emulate in the areas like: environment of the college, rules and regulations and culture and atmosphere.

Social Maturity: This is achieved through all programs within the class room and outside promote interactions, co-operation, collaboration, mutual help, concern for others and service.

Business Acumen: Being a business management institute and all courses being professional and job oriented, students are oriented to sharpen their business talent and business acumen through teaching, guidance and industry interactions.

Professionalism: The College aims at creating perfect people who will be outstanding professionals in whatever areas of work they choose.

Employability Skills: The institute has a full time training and placement officer. A variety of certificate programs are offered by the college in addition to regular course to promote employability of the students. Training in soft skill is imparted in all courses. Projects and practical's give a firsthand idea of job situations.

Scientific Temper: Opportunity is provided in the curriculum delivery to promote scientific thinking, spirit of questioning, expression of creative ideas, experimentation and learning by doing.

Strategic Thinking: The institute strives to make the students pro-active to identify and encash opportunities.

Values & Ethics: The institution is secular in its admissions, appointment and approach. Equal dignity is given to both rich and poor students. Students respect teachers and students are recognized by the teachers. Equality of opportunity is provided to both gender.

The delivery of the content of the programme is aimed at achieving the learning outcomes. All the staff are involved in creation of a learning environment. All students are valued equally during their learning journey with the Institute. Accordingly, the curriculum, teaching and learning and assessment at college are student centric.

Institutional Initiatives to Enhance the Social and Economic Relevance of the Courses Offered:

The college has taken initiatives to enhance the social & economic relevance of the courses namely quality jobs, promotion of entrepreneurship, innovation and research aptitude through various components parallel to curriculum delivery.

Table 1: Initiatives taken by the college to enhance the social & economic relevance of the courses.

Course	Quality Jobs	Entrepreneurship	Innovation	Research Aptitude
MBA	1. Offering Specializations in the program to become full-pledged professional in the corresponding area such as marketing, finance, production, HRD & Systems. 2. Dual Specialization offered by the Institute. 3. Training & Placement services. 4. Soft skill & Communication Training.	1. Certification programs : 2. EDP as supplement to the course.	1. Programms such as MAGMA, MANEGMA, MATRIX. 2. Compulsory participation in exhibitions for subjects like Marketing & Economics	1. Project work, 2. Industry Placement. 3. Business Case Development
MCA	1. Offering Specialization 2. Choosing Electives with greater social & Economic relevance. 3. Training & Placement services.	1. Certification programs :	1. Esparenza 2. Manegma 3. Domain knowledge Seminars	1. Team Project work. 2. Mini Project 3. Individual Project in

	4. Soft skill & Communication Training.			Industries.
MSW	1. Training & Placement services. 2. Soft skill 3. Communication training.	1. Certification programs : 2. NGO Management Training.	1. Manthana 2. Manegma 3. Vivekanda Study Circle 4. HR-Galaxy	1. Summer Placement. 2. Compulsory Project work 3. Field Case Report.
BCA	Soft skill & Communication Training	1. Certificate Programs	1. Encouragement for software development & maintenance.	1. Team project work in three semesters. 2. Compulsory Project work in 6th semester
BBM	1. Equipping for entry level jobs through orientation & skill building. 2. Interaction, Communication & Leadership Training.	1. Certificate Programs	1. Exposure to retail marketing	1. Compulsory Project work in 6th semester
B.Com	Equipping for entry level jobs through orientation & skill building.	1. Certificate Programs	1. Exposure to Computer based Auditing	1. Compulsory Project work in 6th semester

3. Learning Outcomes:

The Institutions Effort to Collect and Analyse Data on Student Learning Outcomes and Use it for Planning and Overcoming Barriers of Learning:

The Institute collects and analyse feed back in the following manner-

- ✓ **Internal Assessment** - Through internal examinations, assignments, presentations, seminars the faculty are able to assess the achievement of the expected learning outcomes. The barriers of learning are overcome through individualized attention, student centric counselling, and parental motivation.
- ✓ **Examination Result Analysis** - The result analysis of every student provide the academic progress of the student. This is used for feedback on student progress. This analysis is used for planning the pedagogy and lesson in the consecutive semesters.
- ✓ **Faculty Observation** - The faculty assess the students through their class participation as well as involvement in student activities. Weightage is given to supplement their internal marks through EC & CC (Extra-curricular and co-curricular activities).
- ✓ **Mentor Process** - Through a standard mentor format, the internal/external mentor suggest some measures for improvement.
- ✓ **Employer Feedback Analysis** - The placement department collects feedback about the student performance in the industry during their initial period of employment. This information is analysed to ascertain the industry readiness of the student. If any common deficiencies are noted in the students, training programmes will be re-designed for the successive batches.

- ✓ **Parents Feedback** - The College seeks parent's feedback of successful students and incorporates their learning outcome for the improvement of struggling students.

Monitor and Ensure the Achievement of Learning Outcomes by the Institution:

The institution has a clearly defined, set mechanism to monitor the learning outcomes. The student SWOT Analysis is one of the important basis to find out their skills, strengths, interest in activities, career objectives and expectations from the institute. This will be used as a reference to monitor the student progress and achievement of learning outcome.

Attendance is compulsorily taken for every lecture, guest lecture, workshops, training and other value added programmes offered to the students by respective class lecturer or co-ordinator of the departments. In case of regular absence to the programmes the student will be counselled by the faculty members.

Regular internal assessment tests, presentations, case analysis and quizzes are conducted to ensure the subject learning of the students. After industrial visits, the placement team insists on written report on applicability of theoretical concepts in the real scenario to ensure the expected learning outcome. To assess the positive impact of the trainings on employability skills, mock tests are given. Mock interviews are conducted by a team of faculty to check on their readiness of the student to meet the industrial requirements.

Use of Assessment/Evaluation as an Indicator for Evaluating Student Performance, Achievement of Learning Objectives and Planning:

Continuous Student Evaluation includes assessment through internal assessment test, assignments (presentations, case analysis, project etc), class participation, involvement in curricular, co-curricular and extracurricular activities, initiatives and co-ordination of programmes at the institute. This will provide information about the overall development of the students.

- ✓ The institution uses assessment as an indicator for planning the academic activities. The head of the institute considers student evaluation results to give proper directions to the faculty members with respect to teaching methodology, mentoring process and other activities for the improvement of student. For example – If performance of the students is poor in any internal assessment examination, the principal/course co-ordinator will hold a meeting with students to discuss the reasons and take necessary actions. Students' performance in each subject will be considered while planning for the next semester.
- ✓ The various departments/committees also plan activities and student development programmes based on the outcome of the student evaluation process. For example – It was observed by the faculty that many students do not have the required extent of communication skills. This was identified even during SWOT analysis and mentoring Process. Placement & training department initiated communication development training programme for all P.G. Courses. The English language instructor of the college takes additional spoken English classes for under graduate students of all courses. This apart, the college conducts certificate programme which is exclusively aimed at improving English language capacity of the students and other soft skills.
- ✓ The faculty members use students' assessment to take necessary measures to improve the performance. This will also help to find whether learning objectives are achieved or not. Faculty will consider the assessment data to

plan for the next semester in terms of class room activities, assignments and teaching methodology. For example – tutorial classes are conducted by the faculty members based on the performance of the students in internal assessment test and their participation in class.

- ✓ Mentors will use assessment data to suggest learning techniques to the mentees for improvement.
- ✓ Evaluation process helps in selecting students for various intercollegiate competitions (management events, business plan, paper presentation and cultural competitions). It also helps to initiate some supporting course or improvement programmes to achieve expected learning outcomes.

Other Relevant Information Regarding Teaching-Learning and Evaluation:

- ✓ Through its "First Come First Serve" model, in attracting admissions, the institution provides opportunity to all kind of students who have a strong desire to change in their life.
- ✓ The pedagogy is geared to be Student Supportive. Students are encouraged to be achievers.
- ✓ The unique "Save a Year program" allows to enhance their attendance by taking additional classes in the concerned subject so that a student who has missed classes can still have an opportunity to appear for final examinations. Although limited to one time in the duration of a course, this is an opportunity for the students to rectify their mistake and to continue in the mainstream.
- ✓ "Earn while Learn" Program support economically poor students by providing them chances to take up part-time jobs either in the college or outside.
- ✓ Competency of the students are enhanced by providing "Value Added Chapter" in all subjects in each semester.
- ✓ Teaching - Learning process is made more effective by providing "High Tech Class Rooms" with LCD projector, audio amplifier; Wi-Fi based Internet facility and CCD Camera Monitoring in all class rooms.
- ✓ "Student Supportive Materials" like College Calendar, Teaching Plan Booklet, Study Materials, Question Bank for all subjects are provided. Career guidance in the beginning of each semester helps redefine the goal.
- ✓ The Institute also provides "Web Supportive Materials" like Old Question papers, College Magazine & News letters, Placement Brochure, Notice Board, Higher Education & Job Opportunities which can be downloaded by the students from the website of the college.
- ✓ "New technologies" like Biometric attendance for Staff members, CCD camera recording to monitor student discipline are deployed by the institution to supplement and complement student learning.
- ✓ Indigenous software developments by Students are put to use for internal Institutional requirement.
- ✓ MOU/Collaboration with local IT companies on student support for system development.
- ✓ Mentoring Program: The faculty members mentor the students and connect with them on academic & personal aspects on a regular basis.
- ✓ Each and every student subscribes leading Business News Papers for weekly news analysis sessions.

4. Conclusion:

The graduate attributes of the institution clearly define and articulate the learning outcome of the institution. The institution endeavors to achieve the stated

graduate attributes through its various programmes and activities. The case of Srinivas Institute of Management studies substantiates the achievement of intended learning outcomes as central to the pedagogical and assessment processes. Mechanisms are in place to analyze shortfalls in achievement of learning outcomes and suggest improvement measures. The teaching-learning assessment strategies are geared to facilitate the achievement of intended learning outcomes such as intellectual capability, character building, emotional and social maturity, business acumen, professionalism, employability skills, scientific temper, strategic thinking and desirable values and ethics. Besides, the socio-economic relevance of the courses such as quality jobs, promotion of entrepreneurship, innovation and research aptitude are considered while learning outcomes are chalked out.

5. References:

1. Manual for self-study report of affiliated colleges. National Assessment and Accreditation Council. June 2013.
2. Hill, Y., Lomas, L., MacGregor, J., Student:s perceptions of quality in higher education. *Quality Assurance in Education*, Vol. 11, No. 1, pp. 15-20, 2003.
3. Joseph, M., Yakhou, M., Stone, G., An educational institutions quest for service quality: customer's perspective. *Quality Assurance in Education*, Vol. 13 No. 1, pp. 66-82, 2005.
4. Line Wittek, Laurence Habib, Laurence Habib, Quality Teaching and Learning as Practice Within Different Disciplinary Discourses, *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, Vol. 25, Number 3, pp.275-287, 2013.
5. Srinivas Rao A., Suresh Kumar P. M., & Aithal P. S., Strategic Planning in Higher Education Institutions : A Case Study of SIMS - VISION 2025, *International Journal of Educational Science and Research*; Vol.5, Issue 2, pp. 29-42, April 30, 2015.
6. Aithal P. S., Srinivas Rao A., & Suresh Kumar P. M., How Innovations and Best Practices can Transform Higher Education Institutions: A case study of SIMS, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, Vol. 6, Issue 2, pp.83 - 98, 2015.
7. Gopal K. Kanji, Abdul Malek Bin A. Tambi & William Wallace, A comparative study of quality practices in higher education institutions in the US and Malaysia, *Total Quality Management*, Vol. 10, Issue 3, pages 357-371, 1999.
8. Mohammad S. Owlia, Quality in higher education-a survey, *Total Quality Management* Vol. 7, Issue 2, pp. 161-172, 1996.
9. Aithal P.S., Internal Quality Assurance Cell and its Contribution to Quality Improvement in Higher Education Institutions: A Case of SIMS, *GE International Journal of Management Research (IJMR)*, Vol. 3, Issue 5, pp. 70-83, May 2015.
10. Aithal P. S., & Suresh Kumar P. M., Enhancement of Graduate attributes in Higher Education Institutions through Stage Models, *IMPACT: International Journal of Research in Business Management*, Vol. 3, Issue 3, pp. 121 - 130, March 2015.
11. Aithal P. S., Srinivas Rao A., & Suresh Kumar P. M., Quality Enhancement in Higher Education Institutions : A case study of SIMS, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, Vol. 2, Issue 5, pp. 18-31, May 2015.
12. Aithal P. S., How an Effective Leadership and Governance Supports to Achieve Institutional Vision, Mission, and Objectives, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, Vol. 2, Issue 5, pp. 154-161, May 2015.

13. Aithal P. S., Strategy Development and Deployment in Higher Education Institutions, *Elixir International Journal*, 84, pp. 33594 – 33597, 2015.
14. Aithal P. S., Faculty Empowerment Strategies in Higher Education Institutions. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 5, Issue 7, pp. 108-115, July 2015.
15. Aithal P. S., MBA++ as a Unique & Successful Model in Integrated Development of Business Executives. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 5, Issue 7, pp. 124-133, July 2015.
16. Aithal P. S. and Suresh Kumar P. M., Applying SWOC Analysis to an Institution of Higher Education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 5, Issue 7, pp. 231-247, July 2015,
17. Aithal P. S. and Sridhar Acharya P., Techniques for Electric Energy Auditing in Education System. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 5, Issue 7, pp. 318-325, July 2015.
18. Aithal P. S., Suresh Kumar P. M. and Deekshitha, Societal Expectation and Institutional Accountability in Higher Education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 5, Issue 7, pp. 361-373, July 2015.
19. Aithal P. S., Suresh Kumar P. M. and Pavithra Kumari, Methods and Approaches for Employability Skill Generation in Higher Educational Institutions. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 5, Issue 7, pp. 390-410, July 2015.
20. Aithal P. S. and Harischandra P., Quality Enhancement in Higher Education Institutions through Best Practices in Library: A Case of SIMS. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 5, Issue 7, pp. 489-505, July 2015.
21. Reshma, Shailashree V. T, Sridhar Acharya P., and Aithal P. S., Analysis of Academic Administrative System Implemented at SIMS. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 5, Issue 7, pp. 771-787, July 2015.
22. Pradeep M.D, and Aithal P. S., Learning through Team Centric Exercise & Key Point Pedagogy - An effective Learning Model for Slow Learners in Higher Education Training, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research & Development*, Vol. 2, Issue 9, pp. 265-270, September, 2015.
23. Aithal P. S. & Suresh Kumar P. M., Opportunities and Challenges for Private Universities in India, *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 6, Issue 1, pp. 88-113, January 2016.
24. Aithal P. S., & Suresh Kumar P.M., (2016) Innovations in Private Universities : A Case of Srinivas University, *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 6, Issue 1, pp. 250-264, January 2016.
25. Aithal P. S., Creating Innovators through setting up organizational Vision, Mission and Core Values : a Strategic Model in Higher Education, *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 6, Issue 1, pp. 310-324, January 2016.
26. Aithal, P.S., Comparative Study on MBA Programmes in Private & Public Universities - A case study of MBA programme plan of Srinivas University, *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research (IJMSBR)*, Vol. 4, Issue 12, pp. 106-122, 2015.
27. Aithal P. S. & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, Impact of On-line Education on Higher Education System, *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern*

- Education (IJERME) (www.rdmodernresearch.com) Vol. I, Issue I, pp. 225-235, 2016.
28. Aithal P. S. & Jeevan Pinto, Innovations in Higher Education - A new model implemented in MCA degree programme of Srinivas University, International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME), Vol. I, Issue I, pp. 275-289, 2016.
 29. Sridhar Acharya P. and Aithal P. S., Environmental Consciousness in Higher Educational Institutions : A case of SIMS, International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME), Vol. I, Issue I, pp. 273-284, 2016.
 30. Aithal P. S., and Suresh Kumar P.M., Analysis of Choice Based Credit System in Higher Education, International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME), Vol. I, Issue I, pp. 278-284, 2016.
 31. Aithal P. S., Innovations in Student Centric Learning – A Study of Top Business Schools in India, International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME), Vol. I, Issue I, pp. 298-306, 2016.
 32. Aithal P. S., Innovations in Experimental Learning – A Study of World Top Business Schools, International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME), Vol. I, Issue I, pp.360-375, 2016.
 33. Aithal P. S., How to Increase Research Productivity in Higher Educational Institutions –SIMS Model, International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME), Vol. I, Issue I, pp.447-458, 2016.
 34. Aithal P. S. & Suresh Kumar P. M., Academic Support through Information System: Srinivas Integrated Model, International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME), Vol. I, Issue I, pp.376-384, 2016.
 35. Aithal P.S., & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, An Innovative Education Model to realize Ideal Education System, International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM), Vol. 3, Issue 3, pp. 2464 - 2469, March, 2015.
 36. Aithal P. S., Shailashree V.T., & Suresh Kumar P.M., ABCD analysis of Stage Model in Higher Education, International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE), Vol. 6, Issue 1, pp. 11-24, January 2016.
 37. Aithal P. S., Shailashree V.T., & Suresh Kumar P.M., Analysis of NAAC Accreditation System using ABCD framework, International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE), Vol. 6, Issue 1, pp.30 - 44, January 2016
 38. Aithal P.S., Shailashree V.T., & Suresh Kumar P. M., Application of ABCD Analysis Framework on Private University System in India, International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research (IJMSBR), Vol. 5, Issue 4, pp. 159-170, April 2016.
 39. Aithal P. S., Shailashree V.T., & Suresh Kumar P.M., The Study of New National Institutional Ranking System using ABCD Framework, International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME), Vol. I, Issue I, pp. 389 – 402, 2016.